

An exploration of data-informed decision making by school leaders in post primary schools in Ireland and internationally

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Research on data use in education has proliferated around the world, encouraged by policy recommendations and the increasingly diverse data that are now available to school leaders and teachers to inform their practice. A new wave of data use in education suggests that data should not completely drive decisions rather data can be used to inform decisions in schools. Meaningful and accurate data allows school leaders and teachers to assess to what extent changes are needed in schools and classrooms and they can implement these changes accordingly. This data, combined with the professional knowledge of educators, can contribute to achievement and learning in schools. The concept of data-informed decision making (hereafter DIDM) is an essential element in school leadership because of the effect it can have on effective learning and teaching and school improvement. School leaders and teachers work collaboratively to use a multitude of different data sources to improve education. This new understanding of data use does not focus solely on achievement on a narrow set of topics but can be used to work on different goals i.e. literacy, numeracy, wellbeing, arts, critical thinking and creativity. This paper examines the literature related to DIDM in Ireland and around the world. It concludes by suggesting that while the concept of DIDM is still in its relative infancy in the Irish education context, there is much work to be done to support school leaders in enacting DIDM policies in post-primary schools.

Key Words: Data-informed decision making, school leadership, school improvement

Highlights

- This paper examines the literature related to DIDM nationally and internationally
- This paper highlights the rationale behind the use of academic monitoring data for school improvement
- This paper concludes that school leaders need support in enacting DIDM policies in post-primary schools.

The notion of data-informed decision making (hereafter DIDM), a name used interchangeably with data-driven decision making (DDDM) and data-based decision making (DBDM) has been used internationally by policymakers, school leaders and teachers for decades. While making decisions has always been part of school leadership and development, the systematic use of data to inform decisions is comparatively new to the Irish education system (Young *et al.*, 2018). This paper will examine the literature related to DIDM both nationally in Ireland and internationally. Having reflected on the literature, this exploration will also provide an insight into the policy context in Ireland. It will explain what data school leaders use and how this data is utilised for school improvement. It draws on my own professional practice as a principal of a post-primary school in Ireland. It concludes by suggesting that while the concept of DIDM is still in its relative infancy in the Irish education context, there is much work to be done to support school leaders in enacting DIDM policies in post-primary schools.

Towards a conceptual framework for data-informed decision making

DIDM refers to the systematic collection, analysis, examination, and interpretation of data to inform practice and policy in the educational context (Mandinach, 2012). It is a generic process that can be applied to classrooms to improve instruction as well as in administrative and policy contexts (Mandinach, 2012). It is best understood as a process embedded in organisational structures, cultures, norms and routines which are not only affected by these factors but also by the knowledge, background and expertise of those using the data (Conklin Bueschel, 2018). Current literature illustrates that data-informed decision making can contribute to improvements in student learning and achievement (Van Geel *et al.*, 2016; Schildkamp, 2019). It is no longer acceptable to simply use anecdotes, gut feelings, or opinions as a basis for decisions (Mandinach, 2012). Certainly the influence of data carries significant weight with

policy makers in the context of education (Spillane, 2012; Van Geel *et al.*, 2016). *The No Child Left Behind* (NCLB) legislation introduced in the USA had a considerable effect on the accountability agenda in this jurisdiction (Congress, 2001). DIDM has also become a key component of education policy and practice in countries such as England, Canada, Belgium, the Netherlands, South Africa, Australia and New Zealand (Datnow and Park, 2014; Schildkamp and Visscher, 2014; Young *et al.*, 2018).

Data can be categorised into four main types: Demographic data including attendance and behaviour records; Student achievement data including standardised testing and formative and summative assessment data; Instructional data including teachers' use of time, patterns of course enrolment/subject uptake and the quality of the curriculum; Perception data including insights regarding values, beliefs, and views of individuals or groups gathered through the use of focus groups or surveys (Datnow and Park, 2014; Gelderblom *et al.*, 2016). The increasing emphasis on the use of data in education is twofold. Firstly, in this climate of globalised education reform and accountability, school leaders and teachers are held to account for the quality of the learning experience that they provide (Young *et al.*, 2018). Data, such as student achievement results on standardised assessments are utilised in a summative way for the purpose of external parties such as parents or the inspectorate. Behind government accountability policies is the idea that teachers and school leaders need to know how to analyse, interpret, and use data so that they can make informed choices resulting in improved student attainment (Datnow and Park, 2014).

Mandinach and Honey's model in Figure 1 outlines the process by which raw facts become information when individuals analyse and summarise them. Data must be synthesized, prioritized and interpreted in order for knowledge to be constructed so that data can affect decisions (Mandinach and Honey, 2008). This model also notes that data use at classroom level is part of a larger context of school and district.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework for data-driven decision making (Mandinach and Honey, 2008)

It is not possible for Mandinach and Honey’s (2008) model to capture all aspects of data-informed decision making. For example, different levels of skill and capacity may determine school leaders’ and teachers’ abilities to engage in the process of transforming data into knowledge. Furthermore, school leaders’ and teachers’ assumptions and beliefs are likely to shape their interpretations of data (Datnow and Park, 2014).

Schildkamp and Poortman (2015) developed a data use theory and added the term *purpose* to the data process describing that data teams begin with a purpose in the form of a problem definition and a related goal instead of with data. Following the development of a problem definition based on data, hypotheses regarding the problem are formulated and *data* to investigate the hypotheses are accessed and gathered. Schildkamp and Poortman (2015) note that while data based decision-making can lead to increased student achievement, schools struggle with the implementation of the process and appropriate and effective professional development in the use of data is necessary. This is echoed more recently in the Irish context by

McNamara et al (2021) who call for a large-scale training needs analysis of schools leading to the upgrading of data use support mechanisms in light of these findings.

Figure 2: Data use theory of action and factors influencing data use (Schildkamp and Poortman, 2015, p. 5)

Data-informed quality assurance: school self-evaluation

International comparisons of educational attainment have increased the level of value placed on quality assurance in schools to enable countries to perform competitively globally (Hislop, 2012; Torrance and Humes, 2015; Brown, McNamara and O’Hara, 2016; Skerritt *et al.*, 2021). Current approaches to quality assurance in schools in most jurisdictions now combine systems of external inspection with elements of internal school self-evaluation (hereafter SSE) (Brown *et al.*, 2020). The literature notes that internal evaluation is compulsory in twenty-seven EU education systems, and where it is not compulsory, it is highly recommended (European Commission, 2015). The Inspectorate in Scotland helpfully breaks

SSE down to three basic questions which go to the core of what the process is about: ‘How are we doing?’ How do we know? What are we going to do? (Her Majesty’s Inspectorate of Education, 2001, p. 7). Schildkamp provides a more detailed definition when she describes SSE as: ‘a procedure involving systematic information gathering that is initiated by the school itself and intends to assess the functioning of the school and the attainment of its educational goals for purposes of supporting decision-making and learning and for fostering school improvement as a whole’ (Schildkamp, 2007, p. 4). This data-based contribution to quality improvement of educational provision leads to a superior student experience and outcomes and improved school performance (O’Brien *et al.*, 2022).

Data-informed decision making and the Irish educational context

The formal re-introduction of school self-evaluation heralded a more formalised adoption of DIDM in Irish schools in order to improve their administrative and academic standards (McNamara *et al.*, 2021). While SSE was a feature in Irish schools since 2003, the process became a formal requirement of schools in 2012 when SSE was re-introduced as a collaborative, inclusive, internal process of review and reflection leading to considered action and school improvement (Department of Education and Skills, 2003).

A key theme in the educational literature centres on the context of new public management and its political ideology of neoliberalism in which SSE has emerged as a widely used data informed approach for school improvement (McNamara *et al.*, 2021). New public management aims to empower schools to develop autonomy around their processes and standards, but paradoxically with an added framework of increasing scrutiny and regulation (Hislop, 2012; Brown *et al.*, 2016). The emphasis on SSE and school improvement supports the neoliberal emphasis on economic, accountability and efficiency in public services evident in the literature (MacBeath, 2005; Macbeath, 2006). Certainly there is a sophisticated

assemblage of interrelating principles, both complementary and contradictory, that contribute to the support for SSE (Savage, 2016, 2020; McNamara *et al.*, 2022).

Student achievement data and data-informed decision making

The use of student achievement data for school accountability has become increasingly widespread amongst education systems across the globe (Brill *et al.*, 2018). Aside from the accountability element, academic monitoring data can also be used to ensure that students are agentic in their progress and are supported by parents and school staff to reach their potential. Despite the increasing international interest in the use of data to improve education, few studies examining the effects on student achievement are available (Van Geel *et al.*, 2016). However, one such study does describe a number of significant benefits to the considered use of academic monitoring data by school leaders and teachers. Data can assist teachers to set and refine concrete goals. Data can assist teachers to decide how to pace their lessons, guide flexible groupings of students and guide students for intervention. Data can be used to highlight inconsistencies between results and assessments, which can indicate when there is a need to review the assessment process. Data can also nurture a culture of inquiry and reinforce school priorities since the information provides for transparent communication between teachers, students, parents and the rest of the school community (Datnow and Park, 2014).

The rationale behind the use of academic monitoring data for school improvement warrants further research. On the one hand, school improvement may mean an integrated curriculum and pedagogy supplemented by systematic, aligned formative assessments which will produce low stakes diagnostic data to improve student understanding of a topic. This will be in direct opposition to the notion of school improvement that answers to an assessment-based accountability system that equates school effectiveness with improved student test results on

high-stakes, summative assessments (Conklin Bueschel, 2018). The almost exclusive emphasis on student academic achievement in accountability systems can ignore the full breadth of student outcomes, attitudes and behaviours that schools develop resulting in potentially narrow summaries of school effectiveness (Prior, Goldstein and Leckie, 2021). International educational policy has grown to recognise the significance of non-academic attainment, for example, the Every Student Succeeds Act (Sen. Alexander, 2015) in the United States, which requires states to report a non-academic performance indicator such as absenteeism. This motivated the use of data for informing teaching and learning practices in schools in the United States but most often, for the intention of accountability and compliance, rather than for school improvement (Mandinach and Schildkamp, 2021).

School leadership and data-informed decision making

There is lack of research on the influence of school leaders on data-informed decision-making practices in post-primary schools. Kinsella's (2021) research is the first study to focus exclusively on the factors impacting Irish post-primary principals' data use practices. School leaders play a key role in driving the practice of data-informed decision making in order to contribute to improving school attainment and teacher professionalism (Datnow and Park, 2014). There is, however, a dearth of advice and information with respect to how data should be used (Spillane, 2012). Relations between data and local decision making are generally not expanded on in policy texts. Instead, policy makers assume that utilising data to make decisions about practice should be relatively straightforward (Spillane, 2012). Yet Spillane (2012) warns against several unexamined and potentially problematic assumptions regarding a simplistic view of data use. Firstly, data do not objectively influence decisions on their own; rather it is people's use of the data they select to negotiate arguments regarding problems and solutions. Such data must always be considered in context. Finally, the use of data is not an unqualified

good; rather people can use data in ways that lead to unanticipated or harmful outcomes. (Mandinach, 2012).

Conclusion

While there is growing support in the literature for the relevance of DIDM as a quality improvement mechanism in post-primary schools both in Ireland and abroad, these approaches to school improvement are not without their critics and require further research for those aiming to improve the quality of the educational experience in the post-primary school sector. It is clear from the literature that the school leaders need support to become data literate in order to use data effectively. It would be worthwhile to survey current data-informed of school leaders and teachers in the Irish context. It would also be beneficial to explore systems used by school leaders and teachers to monitor students' progress and development and to investigate how this data can be used for school improvement.

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